

METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE PEDAGOGUES BASED ON A CREATIVE- PEDAGOGICAL APPROACH

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Abstract: The article examines the theoretical and methodological foundations of developing professional competence in future pedagogues based on a creative-pedagogical approach, the technological system of developing professional competence in future pedagogues based on a creative-pedagogical approach, and the effectiveness of developing professional competence in future pedagogues based on a creative-pedagogical approach. Also, the possibilities of a creative-pedagogical approach to the training of future pedagogues were analyzed.

Key words: future pedagogue, creative-pedagogical, competence, educational, reproductive, retrospective, competence, professional competence, creative-pedagogical approach, technological system, theoretical-methodological basis.

Introduction. In the processes of training pedagogues in advanced scientific research institutes and international centers of the world, the issue of creating axiological relations to national and universal, motivational and valuable activity is considered as a primary means of developing the value system in society, and a tendency to form the educational content based on these relations is observed, and in this regard, several scientific research is being carried out. At the same time, scientific research is being carried out on the development of effective technologies for the development of professional competence in future pedagogues based on the creative-pedagogical approach, and the wide use of the interpretation of the most effective methods of the axiological approach.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Preparation for professional activity, social-philosophical and pedagogical-psychological foundations of professional competence development in future pedagogues based on a creative-pedagogical approach Wilson, J. Kim, Angela Stoff, Benjamin Bloom, Brian Cole, Drapeau Patty, Jaslin Holberg, Merriembar Jeron, O.A. Kolesnik . It was researched in the scientific research of such scientists as Mahkamov, O.Musurmonova,

S.Nishonova, V.Slastenin, D.Roziyeva, B.Khodjaye, Sh.Sharipov, Sh.Shodmonova, Y.Shiyanov, N.Egamberdiyeva, M.Kuronov.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. People are not born creative, but they all depend on the external environment to provide opportunities to realize the potential inherent in each of us at various levels. Creativity is usually seen as the opposite of normal, involving non-traditional approaches. S. Spearman believed that this is "the power of the human mind that creates new content by changing and creating new connections." W. Simpson defined creativity as "the ability to break the generally accepted, usual order of concepts in the process of thinking."

Z.T. Nishanova analyzes many definitions of creativity in her doctoral dissertation and creates a model of creative thinking. He "emphasizes the need to create creative thinking based on understanding, imagination, knowledge, skills, thought, motivation and belief." It is not for nothing that he defines imagination as the basis of creative thinking, because a thought, an idea, an action being carried out, reality first of all appears in the imagination of a person, understanding concepts, acquiring knowledge, skills and the combination of motivation in relation to the situation. According to the analysis of Z.T.Nishanova, a creative thinking process occurs in a person as a result of his awakening.

In our opinion, the concept of creativity is a process related to intelligence, "creativity is the highest form of intelligence", because it includes, in addition to the analysis and use of learned knowledge, the creation of new thoughts and ideas, innovative knowledge.

Our studies and analyzed studies have shown that highly creative individuals can have exemplary intelligence, but those with high intelligence are not always creative.

In order to rise to the level of creativity, a person, unlike others, should seek additional independence, strive to develop his imagination and abilities, creatively and scientifically freely analyze historical and modern literature, be aware of world changes, for this purpose, use mass media and Internet networks. should use it, think freely during the learning process, learn new knowledge with interest and enthusiasm, self-control.

According to our author's tariff, a creative approach is his unusual thinking, ability to respond positively to an unexpected situation, being ready for any question and showing the most perfect result compared to others, as well as activity aimed at creating new ideas as a participant in the educational process.

One of the distinctive features of the development of creativity during the student period is the formation of specialized creativity during this period. In other words, during this period, the motivation for professional activity is in harmony with the development of their knowledge activity, determination of their lifestyle, and the process of individualization.

It is known that any person acquires a certain activity experience as a result of the growth of his professional knowledge. Therefore, a person should create and improve his professional experience with his creativity. Students acquire such experiences as a result of education in higher educational institutions and enrich them throughout their lives. Therefore, in the course of education, it is appropriate for students to master not only the basics of theoretical knowledge, but also to pay special attention to the acquisition of industry-oriented professional competencies and the development of creativity.

We consider it appropriate to reveal the essence of the concept of competence in order to clarify the content of our research in detail.

In modern scientific literature and the legislation of developed countries, it is emphasized that the results of education are determined not only through knowledge, skills and qualifications, but also through the competences acquired by a person during the educational process. Competence is a planned goal of the educational process, which is especially important for the content of higher professional education, it is formed on the basis of professional activity requirements for a specialist and his qualifications.

"Competence is a Latin word that means to achieve, to be right." Competence is the subject's readiness to effectively organize external and internal opportunities to set a goal and achieve it, the subject's personal ability to solve certain professional issues.

According to N.M. Muslimov, the dictionary meaning of the English concept of "somretense" is "ability", but "the term competence serves to express knowledge, skill, skill and ability".

The term "competence" was first used in linguistics in the 50s and 60s of the 20th century and meant the ability of a person to perform an activity. In the definitions of "competence" and "competence" given by A. Khutorskoy and A. Zimnyaya, competence is the behavior and behavior required in a certain activity, and competence is interpreted as the degree of compliance with this requirement, the result of the manifestation of competence. done

V. Serikov defines "competence as the presence of knowledge, skills, education that contributes to personal self-realization" and explains "competence as a skillfully performed action during life."

According to V.I.Baydenko, competence means "the ability or readiness to move (mobilize) all the resources that are relevant in a specific situation, taking into account the purpose of actions and living conditions."

According to the definition of E.F. Zeyer, competence is understood as "interactive constructions that include knowledge, skills, competences, and valuable motivational components, which become an adequate measure of activity."

According to S.Ye.Shishov and I.G.Agapov, competence means the skills of a person based on the knowledge and experience gained during the educational process, as well as his readiness to act.

Competencies are focused on individual independence, academic and practical success.

According to V.D. Shadrikov, competences are formed in the course of a person's professional training and are a new type of subject of activity that implies the systematic manifestation of knowledge, skills, abilities and personal characteristics that enable the successful solution of functional tasks.

B. Kh. Khodzhayev states that most of the definitions given to the concept of "competence" are related to professional education and professional activity, and defines this concept by connecting it with general secondary education. He emphasizes competence as "exceeding the social requirements (norms) for the student's educational preparation, which is necessary for effective productive activity in a certain field."

CONCLUSION. Analyzing and generalizing as much as possible the concept of competence, which is actively used in the educational process today and giving positive results, this concept can be explained in relation to the personality of a higher education student as follows: "Competence" is a student's ability to learn and acquire knowledge in a certain direction, is a preparation aimed at being able to systematize skills and abilities, to use them in practical activities in a way that leads to success.

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